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THE EFFECT OF ONLINE REVIEWS ON PERCEIVED CREDIBILITY AND REVIEW ADOPTION OF CUSTOMERS: THE CASE OF TRAVELOKA VIETNAM

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on determining the extent to which the normative and informational characteristics of online reviews can lead to the possibility of online reviews' credibility, which resulted in the review adoption of Vietnamese users on Traveloka, one of the rapidly growing online travel e-commerce platforms. By exploring the informational and normative drivers of the perceived credibility of online reviews, this research intends to examine the online context. A quantitative technique was used to conduct the study, and 230 survey answers yielded 202 qualifying data. In order to assess the outer and inner models as well as the model fit of the framework, this study applied the Partial Least Squares (PLS) method of the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) approach. The empirical results have demonstrated that the characteristics of online reviews (informational and normative) may increase the credibility of online reviews, which can encourage potential Vietnamese users of Traveloka to embrace new information. The study has also added to the body of knowledge regarding e-reviews by applying certain notable normative cues to the setting of the internet travel industry. The research has also reinforced the need of applying the Information Adoption Model (IAM) and Dual-process Theory proposed by Sussman and Siegal (2003). However, the study is limited by its focus on a single platform and a geographically concentrated sample, which may affect the generalizability of the findings. Finally, the study results have revealed that informational and normative influences of online reviews can generate the perceived credibility of customers significantly, leading to the adoption of reviews; and also have provided recommendations that might be helpful for Traveloka and other travel-related businesses in increasing Vietnamese awareness.

KEYWORDS: Review Credibility; Review Adoption; Travel Industry; Effect.

1. INTRODUCTION

As online shopping was so much more prevalent than its physical counterpart (offline shopping), online users were more likely to depend on online customers reviews of other consumers to come up with a purchase choice (Hennig-Thurau & Walsh, 2003) rather than information obtained from ads or specialists. Prominently, Hennig-Thurau and Walsh found that this propensity occurred by the perception that the comments and recommendations are self-perception, impartial, objective, and independent opinions. Hence, the research and analysis of customer feedback further the progress of business strategy and comparative shopping for individual customers.

In addition, information credibility is a critical indicator of a consumer's online action [1]. There is no reason for customers not to adopt the online information that they perceive as reliable. When looking for online product information, customers tend to consider the credibility of eWOM more carefully than traditional WOM, and they will only take online reviews and recommendations they perceive as reliable [6]. Therefore, examining how people perceive the reliability of online reviews and how they adopt the online review messages can be considered as a noticeable and compelling topic that might increase the information process, especially in the travel market.

In the tourism sector, the travel industry has spent extensive efforts to develop an online presence. Particularly, travel e-commerce sites and review websites make up the majority of the online travel sector. Travel products, especially flight tickets, accommodation, rental cars are able to be bought directly on the company's websites or online travel agencies. Recently, consumers are increasingly likely to plan their own vacations, particularly through OTAs. Those online agencies enable customers to make reservations conveniently from home and frequently provide customers with package discounts and cost-saving solutions. Thus, many tourists now book their vacations through online alternatives instead of talking traditionally face to face with travel firms.

According to an eMarketer study in 2008, it revealed that 61% of customers rely on online customer reviews and other types of eWOM when making a buying decision. Specifically, tourists take advantage of online customer reviews (OCR) to communicate to others their experiences and points of view on travel-related products and services, as well as their levels of satisfaction (Yoo & Gretzel, 2008). As a result, from a business perspective, it is

crucial for marketers and hotel managers to understand how the information provided by online reviews affect customers' decision-making process, with a view of examining the relationship between online review and companies, and how the attributes of OCR influence customers' perception and decisions when making reservations (Filiari & McLeay, 2014; Ye, Law & Gu, 2009).

Besides, owing to the high population and burgeoning tourist industry, Vietnam has experienced substantial development in online travel prior to the COVID-19. In 2020, travel, mobility, and lodging accounted for the biggest e-commerce spending among internet users in Vietnam despite the COVID-19 epidemic. In research from Statista (2020), nearly 60% of Vietnamese respondents said they had used an online travel agency. Among internationally online travel agencies, Booking.com, Agoda, and Traveloka were recognized as the most popular travel platforms that dominate the Vietnamese market. Lastly, this study chose Traveloka as the case study to test because the company is one of the fastest-growing and most well-known travel e-commerce platforms and becoming a leading company in the travel fields for its background circumstances and objectives.

According to traditional communication theories, a customer's evaluation of the information is primarily influenced by informational key elements, such as the source, message, and receiver [68]. For instance, a review's credibility is based on the dependability of sources and the strength of its arguments. However, given that most online reviews are text submissions made by strangers, it is not obvious whether these informative factors would still be significant or adequate in online review evaluation. Moreover, one of the outstanding features of online review discussion is a great ability for social aggregation. Thanks to the Internet, it is more convenient to access more different group opinions because comments from various customers can be compiled and posted online. Particularly in the prevalence of online platforms, such travel e-commerce, it is also unclear how normative factors in these online platforms might affect customers' perception and evaluation of online review's credibility.

Academically speaking, the expected findings of this research are to clarify and offer helpful implications about issues for marketing and commercial operations, notably for the travel sector in Vietnam. The results of the study will reveal evidence about the relationship between the credibility of online reviews and the adoption of

reviews by Vietnamese customers who have used the Traveloka platform at least once (for reading, booking, etc.). These study findings will then be used to contribute and support future studies that will examine the relationship between credibility and adoption.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical Background

The dual process theory is used as the theoretical foundation for this study in order to investigate how and to what extent two types of factors (informational and normative) impact the persuasiveness of online consumer evaluations. It is also claimed that the reader's assessment of the information's credibility is influenced by both normative and informational factors.

The study of McKnight and Kacmar (2006) proposed a research model of what first determines the credibility of Website information. It is because only fewer studies examined elements influencing the credibility of website advise as well as due to the fact that credibility increases customer loyalty and

readiness to follow advice. Thus, the study by McKnight and Kacmar demonstrates that first credibility for website content can be established without the use of experiencing elements. In this study, it will be based on the McKnight and Kacmar model to propose the research framework.

Informational Adoption Model (IAM), first proposed by Sussman and Siegal (2003), can assist researchers in explaining how a person adopts messages and how that information may have an impact on their own behaviors and motivation in the computer-mediated communication. Thus, this study is based on the initial model of IAM with a modified factor that will be presented in the following chapters, focusing on the online customer reviews.

2.2. Hypotheses And Model

This study proposes the research model, as illustrated in Figure 7 below, which is constructed based on Dual-process Theory and some prior literature and previous research. All the hypotheses in the construct would be discussed further.

Figure 1: Proposed Research Framework.
(Adapt From Cheung Et Al., 2009).

H1: Argument strength will affect the perceived review credibility.

H2: Negatively framed online reviews will be perceived as more credible than positively framed online reviews.

H3: Online reviews in two-way communication will be seen as more trustworthy than one-way communication.

H4: The source credibility will have an impact on the perceived review credibility.

H5: Confirmation of prior belief in a person will

positively impact on perceived review credibility.

H6: Online review consistency will positively impact on perceived review credibility.

H7: Online review rating will positively impact on customers' perceived review credibility.

H8: Perceived review credibility will impact positively on customer's review adoption.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this study, the quantitative method is applied

in order to generate the data, to test and evaluate the hypotheses and will rely on descriptive research.

This study will approach simple random sampling and randomly choose the respondents (200-250 in total), who used Traveloka website and read other reviews to consider booking accommodations, focusing on Ho Chi Minh City. In addition, this research will be conducted on the primary data, collected from the survey. In this research, the survey questionnaire, made by Google Form, is utilized as the main method for gathering data from the respondents. After that, Microsoft

Excel also is used to collect, arrange, and filter data for the analysis.

In general, PLS-SEM technique was utilized to determine the impact of informational and normative factors and the relationship between perceived credibility and review adoption of customers in the case of Traveloka's Vietnamese customers.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

4.1. Results

Table 1. Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability And AVE

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
ADOPT	0.857	0.860	0.897	0.636
ARGU	0.776	0.782	0.870	0.690
BELIEF	0.785	0.787	0.903	0.823
CONSIST	0.611	0.611	0.837	0.720
FRAM	0.742	0.750	0.885	0.794
PERC	0.722	0.729	0.843	0.643
RATE	0.785	0.788	0.874	0.699
SOURCE	0.752	0.856	0.852	0.659

To confirm the reliability of the constructions, this study first looked at the estimations for Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability (CR). Table 1 demonstrates that most of the constructs' composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha were greater than the respective threshold criteria values. As an acceptable level of instrument dependability, Fornell and Larcker recommended a composite reliability value of 0.70 or higher and a Cronbach's alpha of 0.70 or higher [29]. As can be seen from Table 6, review consistency, which had a Cronbach's alpha of 0.611 and Composite reliability (rho_a) of 0.611, was recognized as a study limitation.

The research model was put to the test using partial least squares (PLS). PLS is a component-based method to estimate that uses latent structural equation modeling [45]. To measure the effect of the

relationships proposed in the proposed research model, the first thing is to analyze path coefficients. By using a PLS bootstrapping with 500 subsamples, the significance levels for each path could be determined.

The output of the structural model, including the results of t-statistic and p-value in the bootstrapping method is shown in Table 5. Both of the determinants of normative influence (H6 and H7) and three of the five informational influences (H1, H4 and H5) were also supported. However, the model does not account for review framing and review sidedness because of those p-values above 0.005 (0.946 and 0.692 respectively); hence, H2 and H3 must be rejected. To summarize, based on the results in Table 5, all the hypotheses were accepted with the p-value below 0.005, with the exception of H2 and H3.

Table 2: PLS-SEM Path Analysis Results.

	Relationships	T Statistics	P Values	Results
H1	ARGU → CRED	4.208	0.000**	Accepted
H2	FRAM → CRED	1.127	0.260	Rejected
H3	SIDE → CRED	0.397	0.692	Rejected
H4	SOURCE → CRED	3.058	0.002**	Accepted
H5	BELIEF → CRED	4.376	0.000**	Accepted
H6	CONSIST → CRED	3.081	0.002**	Accepted
H7	RATE → CRED	2.863	0.004**	Accepted
H8	CRED → ADOPT	14.527	0.000**	Accepted
<i>p** < 0.005</i>				

From the results in Table 9, the SRMR value of the

research model in this study fell in the value of 0.070;

which is below 0.08 and can be considered as a good model fit.

Table 3: The Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (Srmr).

SRMR	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
	0.070	0.070

4.2. Discussions

This research examined how customers in an online travel e-commerce platform, such as Traveloka, perceive the credibility of online travel reviews, based on the dual-process theory of information process. It also investigated how much a review posted by another online user is adopted as a result of perceived credibility. According to the findings of the data analysis, it was discovered that informationally influences, particularly argument strength (H1), source credibility (H2), and confirmation of prior belief (H5), had a substantial impact on perceived review credibility, in the case of travel e-commerce platform - Traveloka. These results are in line with previous study, including studies of a research of Zhang and Watts (2004) on an online travel platform focusing on information shared among backpackers, Cheung et al. (2009) on an popular online discussion forum that was used daily by customers in China, and study of Park, Lee, and Han (2007) on a virtual shopping website that included information from both sellers and consumers [50].

The findings show that three informational variables are significantly influential components during two-way conversation on the travel e-commerce platform like Traveloka. Readers can utilize the reputation of an online reviewer for credibility as a key signal to evaluate the quality of the review content, the reason being that review quality is also crucial, so users do not just believe the review comments unconditionally. Moreover, receivers continue to put trust in credible and strong arguments despite the existence of normative information. Additionally, if a review receives online conflicts or debates with what they already know and perceive, they are more likely to doubt its reliability. It's because consistent information among reviews and prior experiences tends to be accepted and trusted more by people. The reason for this could be because Vietnamese people tend to believe or conflict that online customer reviews about a particular travel-related hotel are usually facts based on the experience and perception of other users because the reviewers must have already booked and stayed in such a hotel before reviewing it.

Another two factors of informational influence – review framing (H3) and review sidedness (H4) – were not supported by the study, which were

consistent with prior research (Cheung et al., 2009). One potential explanation is that when considering online reviews, some informational variables are more important than others. There is another reason for the lack of support in these two hypotheses. The comment review list attached in the survey contains much more positively-framed and two-sided reviews. As a consequence, the lack of answers based on negatively or one-sidedly framed reviews may be the cause of the insignificant findings on review framing and sidedness.

This study also discovered that, along with the informational factors mentioned in prior studies [64, 71], normative influence cues have a considerable impact on how people assess the reliability of online review. In the online context where socially aggregated normative cues are accessible easily, this contributes that normative influence must be considered in order to figure out the effectiveness of online reviews. In the data results, review rating and review consistency were supported. Which means Vietnamese users are able to assess the online reviews by using these normative cues thanks to the advantage of travel e-commerce platform. Customers are more likely to believe the same review experience if it is regularly commented by different online users (review consistency). Users can also perceive how other readers feel about an online review thanks to the rating of other previous users, which increases the perceived credibility. As a result, normative cues are able to combine with informative cues in the virtual review context.

This is consistent with earlier studies in some aspects of marketing, psychology, and information adoption (Gawronski, Bertram & Creighton, Laura. (2013); Cheung et al. (2009); Sussman & Siegal, 2003), which have shown that customers are more likely to accept and adopt online reviews if they believe them to be trustworthy and valid. In other words, the higher credible online reviews are, the better the customers adopt the review information.

Also, in line with the findings in Table 9, the SRMR value in this study made up to 0.070 and is regarded as a good research model fit. The two results showed that (1) the designed manifest variables explained more than 50% of their variance, and (2) the validity and reliability of the research framework were supported. To recapitulate, the credibility of online reviews has the potential to have

a positive or negative impact on the review adoption of customers, according to the viewpoints of many experts, and marketers. Moreover, the Vietnamese gravitate towards accept, adapt, and depend only on the strong and valid online reviews when reading the online comments of other customers on the Traveloka website or app.

5. CONCLUSION

The studies support both informational influence and normative influence that driver effects on perceived review credibility of customers in online travel platform contexts, such as Traveloka. It has also been discovered that review credibility noticeably affects review adoption. The perceived credibility of online reviews was significantly affected by two normative elements (review consistency and review rating) as well as three informational factors (argument strength, source reliability, and confirmation of prior belief). Review framing and review sidedness, according to the analyzed results, were discovered to be insignificant. The study offers some noticeable theoretical contributions by applying dual-process theory in the setting of a travel e-commerce context. Normative influences have a substantial impact on the credibility and adoption of online reviews. The moderating impacts of two common situational elements are also further examined. What is more, this study expects that it will specifically investigate the cognitive mechanisms involved in processing online consumer suggestions from the receiver's point of view.

6. LIMITATION

The study, it must be said, had certain shortcomings. The first was the potential for response bias. Users who were interested in online reviews may have been willing to read and complete the online survey, even though the survey was randomly spread to all members in different ages. Second, the questionnaire survey is limited to one travel e-commerce platform, Traveloka, with restriction to reviews in only one 5-star hotel. As a result, notice must be taken to avoid generalizing problems too far from the specifics of this study. However, the findings ought to be applicable and valid to other travel e-commerce platforms on the internet, particularly those with the same customer target as Traveloka. In the end, Cronbach's alpha for review consistency, which is below the recommended standard of 0.70, was 0.611.

With a view to thriving and growing a travel e-commerce platform, it is crucial to figure out how

customers regard the reliability of online reviews. This is due to the fact that a high degree of e-review credibility will increase the willingness to adopt the online comments and, in turn, will encourage customers to visit and search additional customers' reviews. Besides, it increases the reviews' values, which eventually support the customers when adopting the reviews.

7. RECOMMENDATION

In this study, the findings offer marketing practitioners or managers of e-commerce platforms, especially travel industry, with instructional ideas and suggestions for the factors affecting perceived e-review credibility. Particularly, the findings also indicate that among the different informational elements, argument strength and source reliability are the most important, and in line with other earlier research, to control the cognitive functions of the receivers.

Hence, the company of travel e-commerce platforms might concentrate on ways to raise the quality and source credibility (i.e., reputation) of online reviews. In other words, the business could allow customers to post reviews based on the given frame such as templates of product aspects that could be valid and included in messages (e.g., accommodations, cleanliness, service satisfaction, hotel aesthetics, view) to submit useful product evaluations, such as hotel. For instance, the web evaluations have to provide thorough details, valid statements, and a short summary of the advantages and disadvantages. Additionally, a method for prosecuting offenders might be helpful in addressing the problems with spam, fake, or unreliable online reviews. Customers should be able to report any invalid, fraudulent and seeding reviews that distort the truths or being uninformative, inappropriate, or attach virus links. Moreover, the travel business/agencies should create award programs to honor trustworthy customers who frequently contribute high-quality reviews (based on number of reviews posted, rating votes by others) in order to boost the source (reviewer) credibility reputation.

Normative impact also made a big difference in this study. The travel business/agencies could try to find ways to adapt and develop the normative aspects of the online reviews, making it easier for the potential customers to perceive the reviews' credibility because, in addition to informational cues, these are also crucial for readers, even though travel companies could not directly exert manage and adjust over the content of normative information. Marketers (such as digital marketers) should create

review-rating systems or show social data in a way for readers to make use of the normative information easily. Recommendation to this is to improve the rating system to allow high-quality reviews with several features which are perceived to be important to review readers. For example, people could mark scores on the argument strength of the review, usefulness, the level of understanding, and other factors, rather than just providing a general evaluation score. In travel e-commerce platforms like Traveloka, readers with confirmation of previous

knowledge or beliefs rely much on review ratings; hence, improving the rating system would assist customers in increasing their perception of online review credibility. Another recommendation would be to enhance the searching systems and sort functionality and to allow customers to find online reviews in accordance with different normative criteria, such as display reviews with high ratings to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of information adoption.

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